

To Assess the Impact on Knowledge and Awareness Pertaining to ADR Reporting by Health Care Professionals in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Western UP, India

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Abstract:

Objective: This study was planned to analyze the educational interventions on ADR reporting by health care professional in a tertiary care hospital located in western Uttar Pradesh.

Methods: It is a questionnaire-based study in which pre-test was conducted then session on pharmacovigilance was taken followed by post-test. Scores of pre-test and post-test was compared using chi-square test.

Result & Discussion: It was observed in this study that educational intervention has made an impact on knowledge and increased the awareness among the study participants which has made them to realize the importance of ADR reporting.

Conclusion: ADR reporting by health care professionals has increased after the educational intervention was made. In order to raise awareness and change in attitude regarding ADR reporting, educational interventions at regular interval have played a very important role.

Keywords: ADRs, Adverse Drug Reactions, Pharmacovigilance, Health Care Professionals.

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Introduction

Adverse drug reactions are one of the major contributors in terms of drug-related morbidity and mortality. ADRs are also responsible for increase in hospital stay, decrease in quality of life and increased economic burden. Approximately 35% of the patients experience either one or more than one type of adverse drug reaction during their treatment and hospital stays [1]. As per the World Health Organization ADRs are defined as "A response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for the prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease or for the modification of physiological functions"[2].

In the year 1960, WHO has launched a program for monitoring and reporting of ADRs after witnessing thalidomide tragedy in western countries [3]. In India, ADR monitoring program was launched in 2010 under the Pharmacovigilance Program of India with the objective of safe-guarding the health of the people of India [2].

As per the WHO, Pharmacovigilance is defined as "the science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of

adverse effects or any other drug-related problem"[4]. As health care professionals are the one who prescribe the drugs and in constant touch with the patients through follow-ups are best suited to report the ADRs encountered by the patients during treatment. But due to lack of interest, awareness, attitude and time constraint ADR reporting is not up-to the mark and most of the times they go unnoticed and unreported [3]

Under-reporting of ADRs is a big issue in developing countries as they mostly lack infrastructure for reporting and lack of medication safety monitoring protocols. In India, approximately 10% of ADRs are reported from the south-Indian region. In order to increase the ADR reporting, a culture of ADR reporting has to be inculcated in the health care professionals and various studies has shown that the change in attitude and knowledge has changed the ADR reporting practices among the health-care professionals leading to increase in ADR reporting [5].

Therefore, this study was planned to analyse the impact of knowledge and awareness in behaviour change regarding ADR reporting by Health Care Professionals in a tertiary care hospital located in western Uttar Pradesh.

Aims & Objectives: Following are the objectives of the study as mentioned below:

1. To assess the change in knowledge and awareness, pre- and post-educational intervention towards Adverse Drug Reaction reporting.
2. To assess the impact of sensitisation done pertaining to Pharmacovigilance and safety of the patient.

Materials and Methods: This is a pre-test and post-test questionnaire based cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary care hospital located in western Uttar Pradesh, India.

Study area and participants: Health Care Professionals and second year MBBS students in GS Medical College and Hospital, Pilkhuwa, Uttar Pradesh.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All Health Care Professionals (Doctors, Interns, Nursing Staff) working in Out Patient Department, In Patient Department, Casualty.
2. Second Year MBBS students.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Those who refuse to participate.
2. Those who refuse to give consent.

Study Design: Cross sectional Study.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated by using the standard formula $4pq/d^2$. The sample size to be taken is 510 at standard prevalence rate 16.2% with 5% marginal error.

Study Period: 1 Month (15th November 2021 to 15th December 2021).

Data Collection: Data will be collected on a survey form from the study participants in G S Medical College and Hospital through structured Questionnaire.

Inform Consent: Written consent to be taken.

Statistical Analysis: Scores of study participants according to demographic characteristics will be compiled using student t- test and Chi square test as appropriate. The statistical test is significant at $p < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance.

Ethical Consideration: This study has been approved by Institutional Ethics Committee as per letter number GSMCH/2022/IEC/07 dated 18.01.2022.

Results:

Age Distribution: The distribution of participants across different age groups was analysed to understand the demographic profile of the study population. Among the participants, 414 individuals, constituting 85.4% of the total sample, fell within the age range of 18 to 28 years. A smaller proportion of participants, 43 individuals (8.9%), belonged to the age group of 29 to 38 years. Furthermore, 16 participants (3.3%) were in the age range of 39 to 48 years, while 7 individuals (1.4%) were aged between 49 and 58 years. Lastly, 5 participants (1.0%) were aged 59 years or above. This distribution provides insights into the age diversity within the study cohort, with a predominant representation of individuals between 18 and 28 years old.

Table 1: Age distribution

Demographic Variables	N	%	
Age	18 - 28 yr	414	85.4%
	29 - 38 yr	43	8.9%
	39 - 48 yr	16	3.3%
	49 - 58 yr	7	1.4%
	59 yr or above	5	1.0%

Figure 1: Pie Chart showing age distribution of the study participants

Sex distribution of study participants: The demographic composition of the study population was examined with regard to gender distribution. Among the participants, 224 individuals, constituting 46.2% of the total sample, were male,

while 261 individuals (53.8%) were female. This analysis highlights a relatively balanced representation of both genders within the study cohort, with a slightly higher proportion of female participants.

Table 2: Sex distribution of the study participants

Demographic Variables		N	%
Sex	Male	224	46.2%
	Female	261	53.8%

Figure 2: Sex distribution of the study participants

Table 3: Distribution of Study participants according to Education

Demographic Variables		N	%
Education	Undergraduate	38	7.8%
	Graduate	387	79.8%
	Post Graduate	60	12.4%

Figure 3: Pie chart showing the distribution of study participants according to their education

Distribution of Subjects according to Profession:

The demographic profile of the study participants reveals a predominant representation of doctors. Among the individuals included in the study, 403 (83.1%) were doctors. Nursing professionals constituted the second-largest group, with 70 individuals (14.4%) being nurses. A smaller

proportion of participants, comprising 12 individuals (2.5%), belonged to the paramedic profession.

This distribution highlights the substantial presence of doctors in the study population, followed by nursing professionals and paramedics.

Table 4: Distribution of study participants as per their profession

Demographic Variables		N	%
Profession	Doctor	403	83.1%
	Nursing	70	14.4%
	Paramedics	12	2.5%

Figure 4: Pie chart showing the distribution of study participants based on their profession

Distribution and Pre to Post Comparison of Knowledge Items:

In the pre-test, for Item 1, 103 participants (21.2%) strongly agreed, 174 (35.9%) agreed, 80 (16.5%) were neutral, 97 (20.0%) disagreed, and 31 (6.4%) strongly disagreed. Post-

test results indicated a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing (178, 36.7%). Similarly, for Item 2, there was an increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 254 (52.4%) in the pre-test to 298 (61.4%) in

the post-test, with a significant chi-square value of 9.7 and p-value of 0.045. Item 3 also showed a significant change, with the number of participants strongly agreeing increasing from 159 (32.8%) in the pre-test to 231 (47.6%) in the post-test (chi-square = 24.4, $p < 0.001$). However, no significant change was observed for Item 4, although there was a slight increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 119 (24.5%) to 153 (31.5%) (Chi-square = 8.5, $p = 0.075$).

In the pre-test, for Item 5, 110 participants (22.7%) strongly agreed, 249 (51.3%) agreed, 85 (17.5%) were neutral, 32 (6.6%) disagreed, and 9 (1.9%) strongly disagreed. Post-test results showed a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing (154, 31.8%), with a chi-square value of 17.1 and p-value of 0.002. Similarly, for Item 6, there was a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 95 (19.6%) in the pre-test to 164 (33.8%) in the post-test (chi-square = 36.4, $p < 0.001$). Item 7 also exhibited a significant change, with the number of participants strongly agreeing increasing from 95 (19.6%) in the pre-test to 178 (36.7%) in the post-test (chi-square = 37.3, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, Item 8 demonstrated a significant difference, with the number of participants strongly agreeing

decreasing from 94 (19.4%) in the pre-test to 84 (17.3%) in the post-test (chi-square = 25.9, $p < 0.001$).

In the pre-test, for Item 9, 113 participants (23.3%) strongly agreed, 231 (47.6%) agreed, 112 (23.1%) were neutral, 18 (3.7%) disagreed, and 11 (2.3%) strongly disagreed. Post-test results showed a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing (216, 44.5%), with a chi-square value of 65.1 and p-value of less than 0.001. Similarly, for Item 10, there was a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 165 (34.0%) in the pre-test to 295 (60.8%) in the post-test (chi-square = 81.4, $p < 0.001$). Item 11 exhibited a significant change, with the number of participants strongly agreeing increasing from 78 (16.1%) in the pre-test to 94 (19.4%) in the post-test (chi-square = 19.8, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, Item 12 demonstrated a significant difference, with the number of participants strongly agreeing increasing from 259 (53.4%) in the pre-test to 336 (69.3%) in the post-test (chi-square = 32.7, $p < 0.001$). Finally, for Item 13, there was a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 154 (31.8%) in the pre-test to 243 (50.1%) in the post-test (chi-square = 35.7, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 5: Bar diagram showing distribution and comparison of pre & post-test knowledge items

Distribution and Pre to Post Comparison of Attitude Items: In the pre-test, for Item 1, 103 participants (21.2%) strongly agreed, 203 (41.9%) agreed, 200 (41.2%) were neutral, 48 (9.9%) disagreed, and 4 (.8%) strongly disagreed. Post-test results showed a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing (178, 36.7%), with a chi-square value of 27.1 and a p-value of less

than 0.001. Similarly, for Item 2, there was a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 21 (4.3%) in the pre-test to 58 (12.0%) in the post-test (chi-square = 22.0, $p < 0.001$).

Item 3 exhibited a significant change, with the number of participants strongly agreeing increasing

from 40 (8.2%) in the pre-test to 70 (14.4%) in the post-test (chi-square = 22.4, $p < 0.001$). However, for Item 4, there was no significant difference observed, with the chi-square value of 1.87 and p-value of 0.759, indicating that the responses remained consistent between the pre-test and post-test periods.

In the pre-test, for Item 5, 43 participants (8.9%) strongly agreed, 96 (19.8%) agreed, 61 (12.6%) were neutral, 195 (40.2%) disagreed, and 90 (18.6%) strongly disagreed. Post-test results showed a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing (65, 13.4%), with a chi-square value of 32.3 and a p-value of less than

0.001. Similarly, for Item 6, there was a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 36 (7.4%) in the pre-test to 64 (13.2%) in the post-test (chi-square = 16.8, $p = 0.002$).

Item 7 exhibited a significant change, with the number of participants strongly agreeing increasing from 99 (20.4%) in the pre-test to 188 (38.8%) in the post-test (chi-square = 49.4, $p < 0.001$). However, for Item 8, there was a significant increase in the number of participants strongly agreeing from 221 (45.6%) in the pre-test to 265 (54.6%) in the post-test (chi-square = 16.2, $p = 0.003$).

Figure 6: Bar diagram showing distribution and comparison of pre & post-test attitude items

Discussion

Prerequisite for ADR reporting is knowledge whereas attitude is considered as a determinant of ADR reporting [4]. Either at periphery or at the tertiary care centres a good knowledge and positive attitude towards ADR reporting makes a big difference and help to provide better patient care along with improving the ADR reporting [4]. The present study on knowledge and attitude on ADR reporting has reflected that the health care professionals involved in this study has meagre knowledge and not a positive attitude towards ADR reporting before the intervention was done.

However, after an educational intervention has been made a significant change has been there among the participant which has led to increase reporting of ADRs at the tertiary care centre where

study has been planned. Majority of the health care professionals participating in this study were aware about the pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting but detail knowledge and how to report ADR was lacking which was found in similar studies evaluating knowledge and attitude in ADR reporting [6]. Several studies have similar outcome on ADR reporting after making educational intervention [2] In order to increase in reporting of ADRs various other methods of creating awareness and changing attitude of the patients as well as healthcare workers has been found to be impactful [7] These interventions are helpful in educating the patients as well as healthcare professionals regarding various types of ADRs and safe usage of medicines [7] However, many studies has reflected an uncertainty among the patients as well as health care professionals regarding ADR reporting [8]. So,

studies need to be done to work out on those factors and make strategy accordingly to deal with those uncertainties.

Conclusion

This study has reflected that lack of knowledge and awareness about ADRs along with lack of positive attitude regarding ADR reporting has been the major factor for low reporting of ADRs. However, after educational intervention and detail information regarding ADR reporting and its impact on patient care as well as impact of pharmacovigilance practices can lead to resource optimisation and prevent wastage of resources.

Educational interventions are the most important factor to inculcate the knowledge and help in changing the attitude regarding ADR reporting and strengthening the pharmacovigilance practices in this tertiary care centre.

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